

EMBEDDING FBG SENSORS IN ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING FOR BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors are optical fibre devices widely used for strain and temperature measurements. In biomedical applications, they enable accurate and real-time monitoring; however, conventional surface-mounted configurations suffer from limited strain transfer, reduced durability, and potential detachment from the host structure. Embedding FBG sensors within materials represents a promising solution to overcome these limitations. Additive manufacturing (AM) enables the fabrication of complex and patient-specific biomedical devices, offering new opportunities for sensor integration. Nevertheless, embedding FBG sensors during AM processes remains challenging due to thermal and mechanical constraints, limited process control, and repeatability issues. Strategies for integrating FBG sensors across AM categories according to ISO/ASTM 52900, with particular focus on material extrusion and powder bed fusion techniques. The main embedding approaches, advantages, and limitations are discussed with emphasis on biomedical applications. Finally, current research gaps are identified, highlighting the need for robust and reliable integration methods for next-generation smart biomedical devices.

Index Terms—FBG sensors, Additive manufacturing, Biomedical engineering

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Fibre Bragg Grating Sensors

FBG sensors are optical fibre sensors. They are sensitive to changes in temperature and strain. They are widely used in structural health monitoring and aerospace applications. Recently, they have emerged as an interesting option also in the biomedical field [1]. Their main advantages are small dimensions, light weight, chemical inertness, insensitivity to electromagnetic fields, non-toxicity, and ease of multiplexing. In an FBG sensor, a grating structure is inscribed inside an optical fibre. The grating acts as an optical resonator, causing the reflection of the resonating wavelength, called the Bragg wavelength. The connection between the Bragg wavelength

and the characteristics of the sensor is shown in Eq. 1

$$\lambda_B = 2n_{eff}\Lambda \quad (1)$$

Where λ_B is the Bragg wavelength, n_{eff} is the effective refractive index, and Λ is the grating period. The sensitivity of these sensors to strain is due to changes in the grating period caused by the strain and to the photoelastic effect, which describes the effect of deformation on the effective refractive index. In the same way, temperature acts on the grating period through the thermal expansion effect, and on the effective refractive index through the thermo-optic effect. Applying a strain or changing temperature causes a shift of the Bragg wavelength (red-shift for tensile strain and increasing temperature, and blue-shift for compression and decreasing temperature). The dependence of the shift from strain and changing temperature is made explicit in Eq. 2

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_{B0}} = (1 - p_e)\epsilon + (\alpha + \xi)\Delta T \quad (2)$$

Here $\Delta\lambda_B$ is the shift caused by environmental conditions, λ_{B0} is the Bragg wavelength for a fibre unloaded at ambient temperature, p_e is the photoelastic coefficient, ϵ is the applied strain, α is the thermal expansion coefficient, ξ is the thermo-optic coefficient, and ΔT is the temperature difference.

1.2. Additive Manufacturing

Additive manufacturing is a term that refers to a set of productive techniques which adopt a strategy of production in which material is added layer by layer to build the final product. According to ISO/ASTM 52900:2021 [2] it is possible to categorise the AM techniques in seven groups based on production process characteristics: binder jetting (BJT), directed energy deposition (DED), material extrusion (MEX), material jetting (MJ), powder bed fusion (PBF), sheet lamination (SL), vat photo-polymerisation (VPP). AM is particularly used in industry for the production of prototypes, complex structures, and for products which required a certain level of personalisation. In general, these techniques cannot compete now for large-scale production with traditional techniques (subtractive and casting) in terms of costs and production time. Instead, in the cited example, in which the production is impossible

due to the complexity of the designed product, or for industrial models, in which scale production is not applicable, AM techniques emerged as a breakthrough opportunity. In the biomedical field, AM is particularly interesting for the production of patient-specific devices and tools, and scaffolds for tissue engineering applications [3].

1.3. Aim of the work

In the previous sections, it was shown that FBG sensors and AM are solutions already explored in the biomedical field. The problem with FBG sensors is that usually they are attached to the surface of the device or the implant to be monitored, but in this situation, there is a lack in the deformation transmission from the device to the connected sensor, which results in a worse measurement. Moreover, the sensor on the surface is more exposed to the risk of detachment and damage. So, embedding is a necessity for improving FBG sensing devices, and the connection with AM techniques is necessary to make patient-specific monitoring tools. Despite this, the embedding of FBG sensors during an AM process is not easy due to the risk of damaging the sensors during the process, the lack of repeatability of the embedding process and the possible defect introduced for the embedding. This work aims to investigate the solutions already explored in literature, to expose the improvements and limitations for each of these, with particular attention to the production of biomedical devices. Since this field has emerged in recent years, additional application domains are also reviewed as the underlying FBG embedding strategies in AM are inherently transferable to bio-engineering device fabrication.

2. RESULTS

According to the provided classification, MEX techniques are the most investigated, likely due to the low cost of materials and machinery compared with other techniques. In this case, it is not difficult to stop the process, and the risk of damage caused by heating is quite low. Despite this, the process is not free of problems. In fact, the product can present a low adhesion between the sensor and the matrix in which it is embedded. Furthermore, fibre alignment and repeatability are actual problems for this technique. For MEX, the most adopted strategy is to design a hollow channel inside the device, then stop the manufacturing process, and insert the sensor. Finally, restart the process so that the sensor is embedded inside the device [4]. For PBF techniques, instead, the main challenge is the high temperatures involved in the process. Also, in this case, the main strategy is to stop the process to allow insertion of the sensor, then restart it. The main difference in this case is that the sensor must be protected with a metallic coating. Using a PBF technique, Li et al. [5] produced a smart inter-body fusion cage. For all the other techniques, some examples of embeddings have been found, but without any biomedical

applications, to our knowledge. Nevertheless, the use of these techniques in the biomedical field is well documented [6]. So for each of them, the main strategies for embedding FBG sensors were investigated.

3. CONCLUSION

The embedding of FBG sensors during AM processes is still an open challenge. Different approaches with different AM techniques have been explored, but several gaps remain. Despite this, the opportunity to embed FBG sensors inside biomedical devices during AM process should be explored to design new patient-specific smart devices with an enhanced measurement precision.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Europe Horizon (HORIZON TMA MSCA Doctoral Networks) under Grant Agreement No. 101119738 'MetacMed' (www.metacmed.eu). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The costs of participation in the conference were financed by the Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange in the STER mTSDPAN project (BPI/STE/2023/1/00008).

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Pre-submission